

USING DIFFERENT TYPES OF EXERCISES IN TEACHING READING AT A NON-LINGUISTIC UNIVERSITY

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Abstract: Teaching foreign languages in non-philological universities is one of the most important tasks in training specialists. This article analyzes different types of exercises and the usage of them in teaching professionally oriented texts in English.

Keywords: foreign languages, professionally oriented texts, pre-text exercises, while reading the text, post-text exercises.

The expansion of international cooperation in the field of science and technology requires knowledge of foreign languages from university graduates, the practical benefits of which will be determined by the ability of specialists in a particular field to use information from foreign sources, both oral and written. The problem of language training of future specialists is becoming increasingly relevant. Only the professional orientation of teaching a foreign language provides the possibility of using it as a means of communication, primarily professional. That is why the goal of teaching a professionally oriented language is the formation of professional communicative competence, which will allow the student, and subsequently the young specialist, to communicate and receive information in various situations.

The task of the teacher is to adapt the educational material to a particular specialty. The task of training a qualified specialist is to teach him:

1. Read and understand the original text in the specialty with a dictionary;
2. Extract information from what has been read for the purpose of practical use;

3. Make annotations and abstracts of the read texts, both in Russian and in a foreign language;
4. To conduct a conversation on the problems of the studied specialty.

The main direction in teaching foreign languages in a non-linguistic university is the formation of reading skills in specialized literature and the ability to conduct a conversation in a specialty. Taking into account the experience in teaching the reading of scientific and technical literature, we offer the following scheme for compiling exercises aimed at developing the ability to read, understand and translate technical texts. We can recommend three types of exercises:

1. Pre-text exercises.
2. Exercises performed while reading the text.
3. Post-text exercises.

1. Pre-text exercises

The purpose of developing and compiling pre-text exercises are:

1. Introduce students to the topic of the text and arouse interest in reading the assignment;
2. Motivate students to read this particular material;
3. Explain all the grammatical difficulties of the studied text.

When developing pre-text exercises, the teacher must clearly understand why it is necessary to read this particular text and what knowledge and ideas the student will be able to get after reading this text, and also how the teacher will be able to use this knowledge in further training.

At the pre-text stage, it is advisable to give exercises on correlating the meanings of words with the topic, on highlighting key words, on linguistic guessing and predicting the content of the text. We can suggest the following exercises:

1. Group words according to word-formation patterns;
2. Explain the meaning of the words in the text on the basis of already known word-formation models;

3. Write out internationalisms and find equivalents to them; translate sentences with internationalisms;
4. Write out in two columns the words denoting actions and the performer of these actions;
5. Write out well-known synonyms and antonyms;
6. Find sentences with polysemantic words and remember the different meanings of these words;
7. Find adjectives that could be combined with the given nouns;
8. Write three important factors related to the topic of the text. Brief discussion of the topic.

2. Exercises performed while reading the text

The text stage involves work on exercises aimed at highlighting the semantic supports in the text, dividing the text material into parts. For a more complete assimilation of the text being read, we suggest that students complete the following tasks:

1. Correlate illustrations, diagrams, map drawings, etc. with information from the text;
2. Fill in the gaps in the sentences with information from the text;
3. Translate sentences containing new vocabulary in paragraphs;
4. State what is understood in Russian;
5. Make an overview translation of the text;
6. Make a literal translation of the text.

3. Post-text exercises

At the post-text stage, exercises are offered aimed at controlling the understanding of the main content of the text, at developing the ability to express value judgments about what has been read, the ability to make a comparative analysis of the information obtained in the process of reading, as well as draw conclusions and generalizations.

When compiling exercises of this type, we must take into account the attitude of students to the material they read, how their opinion on this topic changed after reading the text, what new information they received, etc.

The purpose of developing post-text exercises is to teach students the ability to express their opinion about what they have read, as well as to compare the content of the text with their own knowledge, experience, interests and views.

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